

Master in Information Science Research Materials Sharing | Frequently Asked Questions

This document provides answers to frequently asked questions about sharing research materials produced in the context of dissertation work in the Master in Information Science (MCI). Research Data Management refers to the set of practices used to organize, document, store, preserve, and share research materials in ways that support their proper interpretation, access, and reuse. This FAQ focuses specifically on the sharing component of Research Data Management, particularly the upload of dissertation-related materials to Zenodo, in accordance with open science and FAIR principles. A [tutorial](#) has also been prepared to guide you through the process of uploading materials to Zenodo.

Q1: What is a Research Material? A research material includes content produced, collected, organized, or analyzed during the dissertation process. In this context, it may include datasets, presentations, scientific articles, posters, pitch materials, and other research outputs that document or support the work developed by students.

Q2: Why should I share my research materials? Sharing research materials contributes to open science and helps ensure that research outputs can be found, accessed, understood, cited, and reused. These goals are reflected in the FAIR principles, which promote research outputs that are Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable.

Q3: Where should I share the research material produced during my dissertation? Research material produced in the context of the dissertation should be uploaded to the [MCI community on Zenodo](#), which is intended to preserve and make available materials produced by students in the Master in Information Science.

Q4: Who can upload materials to the MCI community on Zenodo? Only students of the Master in Information Science who are carrying out their dissertation may upload materials to the community. To do so, they must first be added to the community with the Reader role.

Q5: How do I obtain permission to upload materials? You should first create a Zenodo account and then contact the community managers or curators with your email address or username so that you can be invited to the community and assigned the Reader role.

Q6: What kinds of materials can I upload? You may upload materials produced during the dissertation process, such as datasets, presentations, scientific articles, posters, pitch materials, and other outputs created in this context.

Q7: Should I place different types of materials within the same upload? In general, each upload should correspond to one main content (e.g., interview), possibly associated with multiple files (e.g., interview script, consent form, transcriptions). If a file is complementary to the main material, it may be included in the same upload, such as a README file accompanying a dataset. If the materials are independent, they can be in separate uploads.

Q8: Should I include a README file? A README file is especially recommended for datasets and other materials that require explanation for reuse. It should describe the context in which the material was created, the variables or abbreviations used, the file structure, the methods applied, relevant links, and any other details necessary for interpretation and reuse.

Q9: In which language should I fill in the metadata? It is recommended that the metadata in Zenodo be completed in English, to improve discoverability and reuse.

Q10: What metadata should I provide when uploading? You should provide accurate and relevant metadata, including the resource type, title, publication date, creators, description, keywords, language, version, and any additional identifiers or related works when applicable. Good metadata is essential to make materials easier to find, understand, cite, and reuse.

Q11: What should I write in the description field? The description should include a summary of the material, the context and purpose for which it was created, the methods or tools used, explanations of abbreviations or codes when needed, and basic instructions for reuse.

Q12: Do I need to assign a Digital Object Identifier (DOI)? A DOI is a persistent and unique identifier assigned to a digital resource. If the material already has a DOI, it should be retained. If it does not, Zenodo can generate one automatically when you select the option to request a new DOI. The DOI becomes active after publication.

Q13: Which resource type should I choose? The selected resource type should correspond to the main material being uploaded. Examples include Dissertation, Dataset, Presentation, Journal Article, or Video/Audio for pitch materials. Choosing the correct type improves indexing and retrieval.

Q14: Should I include co-authors or contributors? For individual materials, such as the dissertation or pitch, co-authors are usually not necessary. In collaborative outputs, such as articles or posters, a supervisor may be included as a co-author where appropriate. Contributors should be added when individuals or entities support the research but are not responsible for the intellectual creation of the uploaded content.

Q15: How should I choose keywords and subjects? You should use keywords that accurately describe the topic of the upload so that it can be more easily retrieved. Zenodo may suggest controlled vocabularies, but additional relevant terms may also be added when needed.

Q16: How can I relate different uploads from the same research project? When completing the metadata of an upload, you should use the fields in the Related Works section to indicate its relationship to other uploads from the same research project.

Q17: Can I share materials containing personal data? Identifiable personal data must not be shared openly. Before uploading materials, you should ensure that data are anonymized and handled in accordance with the [General Data Protection Regulation](#) and other applicable rules. When necessary, Zenodo provides restricted or embargoed access options.

Q18: What access options are available in Zenodo? Zenodo allows different visibility settings: **Public access**, where both metadata and files are openly visible; **Restricted access**, where metadata are public but files are limited to authorized users; **Embargoed access**, where files become public only after a date defined by the student.

Q19: Which license should I use? The recommended option is Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International (CC BY 4.0), which allows reuse and adaptation provided credit is given and changes are indicated. However, another license may be selected if it better fits the material. For software, a non-CC license may be more appropriate.

Q20: What will curators evaluate before approving an upload? Curators will verify whether the upload is within the scope of the MCI community, whether required metadata are complete and understandable, whether the material is sufficiently documented for reuse, whether licensing and personal data issues are properly handled, and whether the upload aligns with FAIR principles.

Q21: Can I contact the curator during submission? Yes. When submitting the upload for review, you may include a message to the curator to clarify any relevant point that is not fully explained in the metadata.

Q22: Can I change or delete a submission after it is approved? Once a submission is approved, it cannot be directly deleted by the student. However, you may create a new version of the upload to update files, metadata, permissions, or visibility settings. In the case of deletion, it may be necessary to contact Zenodo support.